

Recipe Generation System Using Natural Language Processing and Content-Based Filtering

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Abstract—*The recipe generation system uses content based filtering and natural language processing to generate personalised recipe based on what user enters. When a user enters ingredients as input data then corresponding recipe should be generated. This particular research implementation uses Natural Language Processing techniques for normalization ,tokenization, remove stop word, and lemmatization to textual context after processing a dataset of recipes via extract attributes such as titles and components. The filtration of recipe is done by using cosine similarity among the user input and recipes in the dataset via TF-IDF Vectorizer. Streamlit ,a python framework is a user interface used for create recipe generation system*

Keywords— *Culinary Exploration, Natural Language Processing, TF-IDF Vectorization, Cosine Similarity, User Interaction, Personalization*

I. INTRODUCTION

This digital era ,with an overflow of culinary records,it's very hard to get the right recipe baed on user's taste.To slove this problem,we introduce a Recipe Generation System based on Natural language Processing(NLP) and Content Based filtering(CBF) methods.The system pass through different kinds of recipes and extract key information along with instruction and components.To convert textual information to meaningful information,a few NLP Preprocessing step like Normalization, Tokenization,prevent Stopwords and Lemmization were used.TF-IDF Vectorizer ,used for finding similarity among the user input and recipe from dataset for personalized Recipe .The python framework,Streamlit were used for user interface wherein customer had seamlessly have interaction with the gadget. In our method, users are able to discover recipes that are healthy and dietary necessities so as to enhance their culinary reports.

The Recipe generation System preprocess a large amount of recipes first then extract information like ingredients and cooking instructions. This Sytem basically work by preprocessing data using Natural Language processing (NLP) techniques.It had a Tf-Idf Vectorizer used to determine how comparable consumer- input and recipes in the dataset are if you want to produce personalized recipe. In summary, This Recipe Generation is an advanced use of both Content Based Filtering techniques and NLP are able to remodel how customer use recipes on the town. This gadget presents users of all talent ranges and nutritional alternatives with a dynamic and personalized culinary enjoy

through utilising current technologies and intuitive layout principles

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The system for filtering recipes evalvate recipes and uses natural language processing methods to advocate ones that may be cooked the use of the ingrediants entered via a person. To enhance the accuracy of this it preprocesses recipe statistics through lemmatisation, deleting stopwords, and tokenizing them. The next step is to find the maximum recipes with the help of TF-IDF Vectorization, that computes cosine similarity. When users enters ingredients in the kitchen, five best recipes are suggested to them to deliver them a custom designed cooking experience.

In their paper titled "Recipe Recommendation System the usage of Machine Learning Models", S. Maheshwari and M. Chourey[1] advise an technique to slove the hassle of recipe completion with the help of gadget studying algorithm. This examine employs on statistics mining and gadget mastering methodologies for reading meals intake patterns and possibilities. There are two ML (Machine Learning) models used; Vector Space Model (VSM) model and Word2Vec model. The importance of facts analysis and device gaining knowledge of a meals recommendation structures is highlighted through this research

A paper by R., Nantaporn [3] from Human Behavior Analytics Team at National Electronics and Computer Technology Center (NECTEC) in Pathumthani, Thailand offers a framework to offer appropriate meals for children for the reason that there was emergent desires for early life vitamins. This approach uses factor-weighted similarity metrics to achieve both thing compatibility and nutritional cost .The data then subjected to substantial checking out the usage of numerous approaches.

Bień et al. (2020)[5] offers complete examine about cooking recipe introduction the usage of deep learning-based totally language version. The researchers explore

recipe producing equipment, which can be complex and require creativity to make wonderful recipes instead of terrible ones. In addition, by statistics acquisition, evaluation and preprocessing, the authors emphasize at the significance of robust recipe generation fashions. It highlights the significance of evaluating generated recipes the use of Natural Language Generation metrics.

The paper presented by P. Chinnasamy et al.[6] introduces Deep Learning based Collaborative Filtering for Health Recommendation System(HRS), which emphasizes on better approaches in evaluate huge medical dataset in contemporary healthcare device a good way to lead to personalization in presenting suggestions. Consequently, proposed device employs inclusive of Restricted Boltzmann Machine (RBM) and Coevolutionary Neural Network (CNN) amongst others to improve efficiency of fitness care recommendation engines. It offers a performance assessment of this system applied with TensorFlow and Python.

The next paper by Sharma et al. (2023)[8] performed a survey that discovered an green approach which give product advice structures that addresses the growing call for trustable virtual purchasing structures. The research has emphasis on how the advice structures enhance consumer’s degree of buy by 35%. By evaluating, facts coming from Amazon Apparel database that accommodates of 180,000 apparels, this technique makes use of Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) to forecast comparable merchandise. The proposed gadget identifies products with the aid of checking product titles and extracting features described in images using VGG-sixteen architecture which recommends merchandise based totally on densest distance between their characteristic vectors.

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The methods includes using Natural Language Processing (NLP) that rely on user-detailed preferences to generate recipes. First, the textual records should prepeocess, then perform cleanliness and normalization. Then, feature extraction is executed with the help of TF-IDF vectorization. Lastly, cosine similarity among customers input value and recipe vectors are computed so one can become aware of the top recommended recipes and that are then presented to the consumer

The essential steps include in proposed methodology are:

- A. Loading Data
- B. Pre-processing Data
- C. Extracting Features

- D. Calculating Similarity
- E. Generating Recipes

A. Data Collection:

The first step to be done is to load data from dataset. The dataset that contains 14,000 recipe titles, components, instructions, image names in addition to wiped clean ingredients is loaded into reminiscence from special resources which include on line recipe repositories or curated datasets.

```

import streamlit as st
import pandas as pd
import os
import nltk
from sklearn.feature_extraction.text import TfidfVectorizer
from sklearn.metrics.pairwise import cosine_similarity
from nltk.corpus import stopwords
from nltk.tokenize import word_tokenize
from nltk.stem import WordNetLemmatizer

nltk.download('punkt')
nltk.download('stopwords')
nltk.download('wordnet')

import copy

# Load the dataset
@st.cache_data()
def load_data():
    df = pd.read_csv('./Food Ingredients and Recipe Dataset with Image Name Mapping.csv')
    return copy.deepcopy(df)
  
```

B. Data Pre-processing:

The next stage is to preprocess data. First clean up the textual content by way of removing of unwanted phrases and logos, breakdown sentences into character words, and make the whole content to lowercase. Also, use methods like stemming or lemmatization to standardize words and improve the knowledge.

```

def preprocess_data(df):
    # Convert ingredients to lowercase
    df['Cleaned_Ingredients'] = df['Ingredients'].str.lower()
    # Tokenize ingredients
    df['Cleaned_Ingredients'] = df['Cleaned_Ingredients'].apply(word_tokenize)
    # Remove stopwords
    stop_words = set(stopwords.words('english'))
    df['Cleaned_Ingredients'] = df['Cleaned_Ingredients'].apply(lambda x: [word for word in x if word not in stop_words])
    # Lemmatize ingredients
    lemmatizer = WordNetLemmatizer()
    df['Cleaned_Ingredients'] = df['Cleaned_Ingredients'].apply(lambda x: [lemmatizer.lemmatize(word) for word in x])
    # Combine tokens back to sentences
    df['Cleaned_Ingredients'] = df['Cleaned_Ingredients'].apply(' '.join)
    return df
  
```

C. Feature Extraction

For extracting features, here we used includes TF-IDF (Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency) which is the term used to extract features. This includes converting textual information into numerical vectors, specially clean substances from the dataset of recipes. For every phrase in the dataset, the TF-IDF assigns a weight which takes into account both its frequency in the document. These weighted vectors are capable of measuring similarity among user input and recipes with the aid of listening to how vital each word is in recipe descriptions. Cosine similarity is used to find out five recipes which can be maximum similar to consumer's input.

$$tf_{td} = \frac{\text{frequency of term 't' in document 'd'}}{\text{Total terms in document 'd'}}$$

$$idf_t = \log_{10} \frac{\text{total number of documents}}{\text{Total documents with term 't'}}$$

D. Similarity Calculation

Next, the similarity among the user's input and the recipe vectors is calculated to find the best recipes. This is performed with the help of cosine similarity, which measures the cosine among two vectors and levels from -1 to one. Higher cosine similarity rankings advocate more similarity among vectors. The five recipes with the very best cosine similarity scores are the best recipes when user enter ingredients.

```
def recommend_recipes(user_input_df):
    # Initialize TF-IDF Vectorizer with adjusted parameters
    vectorizer = TfidfVectorizer(stop_words='english', min_df=2, max_df=0.8, ngram_range=(1, 2))

    # Fit and transform the vectorizer with recipe ingredients
    tfidf_matrix = vectorizer.fit_transform(df['cleaned_ingredients'])

    # Transform user input using fitted vectorizer
    user_input_vector = vectorizer.transform(user_input)

    # Calculate cosine similarity between user input and recipes
    similarity_scores = cosine_similarity(user_input_vector, tfidf_matrix)

    # Get indices of top 5 similar recipes
    top_indices = similarity_scores.argsort()[0][-5][::-1]

    # Get top 5 similar z
    top_recipes = df.iloc[top_indices]

    return top_recipes
```

E. . Recipe Generation

Then recipe generated in the Streamlit framework, allowing clients to input their choices. Additionally, options for comments or refinement of options can be supplied to further customize the recipe suggestions.

By following those steps, the proposed methodology aims to provide users with best recipe suggestions, facilitating their culinary exploration

IV. RESULTS

The result of a Personalized recipe exploration is made easy and tasty for customers with the help of the Streamlit interface. When customers enter their preferred ingredients, the set of protocols will advocate recipes which can be applicable and easily navigable, entire with names and recipe lists. Customers looking for kitchen ingredients and assist will find out greater usability and engagement thanks to this smooth mixing of textual content-primarily based definitely advice and graphical element.

Fig 1

Fig 2

V. CONCLUSION

The recipe generation system demonstrates effectiveness of leveraging natural language processing techniques to provide personalized recipe suggestions based user inputs. By using TF-IDF vectorization and cosine similarity computations, the system appropriately identifies recipes intently aligned with particular components, imparting customers handy approach of exploring new culinary options. Future work in this area should involve refining the system with customer remarks mechanisms, integrating advanced NLP methodologies, and increase the dataset to encompass a broader variety of recipes and cuisines, thereby enhancing its software and applicability in meal making plans, dietary control, and culinary innovation contexts

VI. REFERENCES

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